

Research Article

<p>ASSESSMENT OF GOOGLE TRANSLATION TEXTS AMONG THE ALBANIAN PUPILS IN PRIMARY AND SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN MALISHEVA AND SUHAREKA MUNICIPALITIES</p>		<p>Computational Linguistics</p> <p>Keywords: Technology, Smartphones, Google Translate, Texts, Assessment, etc.</p>
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Abstract

Nowadays the technology is progressing too fast in any aspect, even in schools. Except the teachers also the learners use the smart phones for their different purposes. A phenomenon is also the Google translate, which the students use the most for their English classes. As a teacher in a primary school we faced with this ‘problem’ if we can call it so. We saw many students using the GT for translating the whole texts from the book and gave it to me without telling me that they used the help of Google translate. So after reading their works we realized that all of them wrote the same text. So now the aim of this study is to explore the students’ purposes of the use of Google translate, attitudes, behaviors and teachers’ assessment for the Google translated texts. This study will help us to know how much do the students’ use the Google translate, how do they use it, if they translate only words in there or a whole text. On the other hand we will know about the teachers on that how do they expect and react the Google translated texts and how they assess those texts, if they give any advises on how to use it or they just give negative grades about that.

1. INTRODUCTION

We all know that Google translate is a world wide web and the majority of people including the students at schools use it a lot. Since we faced this ‘problem’ we were interested to research about its usage in other schools, what other teachers do to stop it or to make it work in educational way. As Google Translate is a free machine of translation and it is easy to use it, that’s why is the most popular app in the world by a very big range of people.

Since technology is in its peak and approximately 90% of the world has smart phones, of course that people are searching for easy ways of understanding a language and they will use apps like GT or other applications just to know the meaning of words or a whole text instead. As Google translate firstly started with two languages, in research of 2016 according to Barak Turovsky, now Google counts 103 languages (Turovsky, 2016). So, in that year the goal of Google translate was to break barriers and to make the world more accessible and now they have hundreds of millions users all around the world.

Since many people are using GT it seems a good option for students too, but we can say that if an adult use the GT it can be quite normal but we cannot say the same for the students, because a student has the opportunity to learn a language with the teacher, where he/she can ask for everything that is interested in, so that’s why the schools exist. On the other hand a lot of students are shy to ask the teacher for many reasons, like they feel ashamed to ask for a word

because they may think that somebody else knows that answer and would laugh with their question or this kind of reasons.

This thing is not good for them because it makes them lazy and their work or passion to learn English would fall. That's why the students are more interested to use translation applications than asking a teacher. Having a mobile phone makes it easier and Google translate is only one click away. The same thing says also Lance Whitney when saying if you need to talk with someone who speaks a foreign language, translate a menu, transcribe a conversation, or dictate in another language, Google can come to your aid with two different apps for iOS and Android devices (Whitney, 2020). This means that even if we do not want to use it, the internet is around us all the time and using new applications whatever they are, we tend to have them in our mobile phones. This started to be a very big issue in schools and a challenge to a fair assessment. Students tend to use it more and more and then we as teachers should be aware when we assess Google translated texts. The main point of my study is how the teachers react to the Google translated texts and how they assess them, since the usage of Google translate is so among us and of course that it will be a challenge for us as teachers to make a fair assessment. According to Paul Stapleton all anglophone universities that have overseas students need to start seriously considering what all this means for their assessment practices (Stapleton, 2019). Will they accept Google-translated essays? Will they embrace seminars mediated by electronic voice interpreters? Will they permit to graduate individuals who lack the ability to understand what is written on their certificates?

This can also happen in our primary and secondary schools and we as teachers should be prepared for any kind of these situations. So assessment will be a very hard process during our teaching English as a second language. It would be so nice for every school if the ministry of education would provide dictionaries for every student. I think that it would be very helpful for them. So in order to use the GT they would use their own dictionaries and also would learn the grammar part of every new word that they would learn at school.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter is going to be about what Google translate is in general, its usage and a lot of definitions from other researchers and authors. There are a lot of different topics on GT but in our study we are going to talk about the assessment of Google translated texts from teachers in primary and secondary schools. Google translate is a very popular free application in the world and the teachers face with it a lot in their classes. A lot of students use Google translate for their homework and they think that it helps them a lot. In our study we are going to present also the pros and cons of using Google translate if it is a friend or foe. We are going to see its accuracy on translation and see if the teachers support its use or not. Many other points are going to be researched in this thesis to see more clearly the basic information for the Google translate and its usage in general.

2.1 What is Google translating?

Google translate is a free multilingual neural machine translation service developed by Google, which is used to translate text and websites from one language into another which was launched in April 2006 (Wikipedia, 2021). Google translate has gained much importance in recent years as it is a world wide web which as we know is mostly used to translate words but also sentences. There are a lot of languages where you can translate whatever you want and you get the translation of the language you want to from it. As the Principal Scientist Franz Och (Och, 2009) has noted that Google translate is constantly working to improve the quality of translation in many languages, in 2009 announced that GT added nine more languages which were Afrikaans, Belarusian, Icelandic, Irish, Macedonian, Malay, Swahili, Welsh and Yiddish. Since many years have passed from this announcement now Google translate counts 109 languages and all of them supported by Google translate as of January 2021 (Wikipedia, 2021).

In the beginning of its usage GT was only a statistical machine translation which used United Nations and European Parliament documents and transcripts to gather linguistic data but in November 2016 Google translate has changed its usage from a statistical machine translation service to neural machine translation engine (Wikipedia, 2021).

2.1.1 How much does it cost to use Google Translate?

Google translate offers free access in it, so it is free to use and that is why every second person in the world use it. Even if it is free to use it does not have all the good things in it. As every other application also the Google translate has its own advantages and disadvantages. According to the editors of Language wire there are some advantages and disadvantages of Google translate:

Advantages:

- Google Translate is free and online 24/7.
- Google Translate is fast- it provides you with a translation in less than 1 second.
- Google Translate bases its logic on human translation.
- The logic is not rule-based and the translation is formed from already translated texts online. The machine is continuously evolving and hopefully will become bigger and better.

Disadvantages:

- Google Translate offers no confidentiality. Everything translated through Google translate is kept by Google, meaning there's always the risk that it could end up in the wrong hands.
- Google Translate offers a 'rough' translation. In reality, it's not actually a translation at all, but just a scanning of related documents, websites etc. And based on this material, the programme generates a suggested text. This explains why you can also experience incorrect content or structure in Google's suggested translation.

- Google Translate offers no form of quality or adaption of the text to specific jargon, layout, industry or market. Basically you can never be sure that the material the machine spits out is correct or way off mark (Languagewire, n.d.).

So even if there are more disadvantages of its use, people still use it for specific purposes, but no one is forced to use it besides it wants to or needs it. As Google translate is reachable 24/7 and it translates in seconds and even if you do not have internet on your phone, that is what makes it worth of use for many people out there.

So about the costs of Google translate use, we can see it into both sides of a medal. It may be free to use it but it can cost you if you are using it to learn a new language, because it can mislead you in that way. As the abovementioned we saw that Google translate is not that accurate because it only scans the words of related documents or websites translated earlier by humans, so it does not use grammar rules, punctuation or humor in it.

We believe that Google translate does not cost you money but it can cost you time and effort if you use it more than it should.

2.1.2 What is the best way to use Google Translate?

As Google translate evolved a lot since its first launch, now there are a lot of tips on how to use it in the best way so according to Makvana (2020) there are 9 useful tips on how to use Google translate in order to communicate better in another language (Makvana, 2020). According to him “Google translate is an extremely useful tool to translate words and sentences from one language to another” (Makvana, 2020). “It supports a number of languages from around the world and you can use this translation service on your iPhone, iPad, Android, and other devices”. As Makvana (2020) has noted, here are the 9 tips on how to use best the Google translate:

- Download translations for offline use;
- Use conversation mode to translate without hassle;
- How to Google translate images;
- Save translations to access them later;
- Make your translations go full-screen;
- Write to Google translate;
- Use Google translate as a dictionary;
- Block offensive words;
- Delete translation history (Makvana, 2020).

Prior research generally confirms that Google translate has its own advantages and for all of them Makvana (2020) gave explanations on how to use them effectively and properly in order to have better translations of words and sentences.

In the other hand Matt Elliot (2018) names some other tips on how to you Google translate the best way and here they are:

- Offline translation
- Highlight text to translate
- Conversation mode
- Save favorite words and phrases
- Use the app as dictionary (Elliot, 2018)

With these tips Elliot (2018), shows that anyone can use Google translate because it is easy to use so you just download the app on your phone and here you go.

The researcher thinks that Google translate is very easy to use especially if you understand a bit English, but anyway GT offers very helpful tips for anyone that wants to use it for any purpose like translating words, sentences, phrases, signs in the traffic and so on.

2.1.3 Is Google Translate accurate?

Much is known about Google translate, but little is known about its accuracy, as Nick McGuire in his study revealed while the Google translate technology is hardly infallible, it's certainly useful in a pinch to translate a few words or phrases. If you've tried it on desktop when translating an entire page, you'll notice it gets the general message across, but is still far from perfect (McGuire, 2019). For this reason it is better to use professional service translations so from human mind, since there are free gaps to fill and a machine cannot do it as a human mind can. As McGuire continues further by saying that Google's latest introduction of neural machine translation is allowing their artificial intelligence (AI) to evaluate the greater context of words and phrases to better mimic a real person, which has lead to smoother and easier to read translations and since now the GT is available for offline use it makes its usage perfect for travelling but despite their best efforts GT is hardly a reliable and consistent translation solution, especially for businesses. Tzounis describes Google translate as a 'machine translation' (Tzounis, 2019). He furthermore says that in many languages one word has more than one meaning or changes its meaning depending on the syntax; and this is where the famous Google translate falls short compared to a professional translator (Tzounis, 2019).

As we know from the abovementioned Google translate now counts 109 languages and there are a lot of language pairs to match and get a translation so for this, Bastin made a study to see which of the language pairs gets closer to human's mind and this table of figure will show us the study made by him.

According to Bastin (2019) the Google neural machine translation (GNMT) system has improved the translation of the two most used language pairs- "Spanish-English and French-English" (Bastin, 2019). "As a result, translation accuracy increased to 85%". "In 2017, Google conducted large- scale surveys among regular GT users. They were asked to evaluate three

translation options: machine statistical, neural and human ones. The results were impressive-translation that relied on neural networks turned out to be near perfect in some language pairs. Below is a table in which the 6-point system for evaluating the quality of translation is used. The maximum score is 6, while 0 is the minimum” (Bastin, 2019)

	Statistical model	Neural Network	Human Translation
English-Spanish	4,885	5,428	5,550
English-French	4,932	5,295	5,496
English-Chinese	4,035	4,594	4,987
Spanish-English	4,872	5,187	5,372
French-English	5,046	5,343	5,404
Chinese-English	3,694	4,263	4,636

“As we can see, the quality of translation in the English-Spanish and French- English pairs is very close to translation made by human” (Bastin, 2019).

As the abovementioned pointed out that Google translate is not that much accurate we confirm my thoughts about it too. From the experiences of the teachers saw that students use the Google translate a lot to translate the texts mostly. This was the reason why I chose to research on this topic and see if this phenomenon is also in other schools.

Since some authors researched and talked about Google translate accuracy they believe that in the future Google translate will improve as a GNMT and its translation will get closer to human’s mind. As this machine translator evolved a lot from its first launch we believe it too, but since we are teachers of a second language we would really like my students to learn translation at school and not by a machine translator as GT is.

2.1.4 How Google Translate works?

Many of us know how to basically use Google translate and we just know some basic tips about it. We use it more to translate from one language to another but we do not know how it really works so according to this, Bell (2019) explains it with the words “machine translation learns like a baby” (Bell, 2019).

As Bell’s (2019) study revealed on that, that “Google translate is just like a child, MT has a brain” (Bell, 2019). Showing this to us we understand that Google translate or MT as professional translators would call it is an empty machine and will be like that until we feed it with words (Bell, 2019). So as much we feed it that much the MT learns. “This is why you should never type made up words into Google translate just to see what it does. When you do, you’re stuffing MT full of potato chips instead of fruit and vegetables. MT will eat anything you feed it” (Bell, 2019). As above mentioned GT in the beginning was only a translation service and from 2016 it is a GNMT “which now uses a new technique called zero-shot translation to teach MT. This replaces

the traditional type of engines. Instead of changing what MT thinks about, they simply changed how it thinks” (Bell, 2019).

From this research we pointed out that MT or GT is a machine translation which needs to be fed in a proper way in order to translate properly. So people should not use it for fun but they should feed it with fruits and vegetables as Bell said.

This study investigation provides us with good information for GT or MT in general. From the usage of GT we see that the machine sometimes does not translate very well, so there might be a problem with the machine or the language we use. The Multimedia-English editors have a good explanation about it (“Multimedia-English”, n.d.). According to them “some languages have fewer translated documents available and therefore fewer patterns that the software has detected” (“Multimedia-English”, n.d.). “This is why our translation quality will vary by language and language pair. We know our translations aren’t always perfect but by constantly providing new translated texts we can make our computers smarter and our translations better (“Multimedia-English”, n.d.).

From our experiences with Albanian language we know that Google translate does not translate that much properly since maybe there aren’t enough documents in MT. So we should feed it more in order to get precise translations. As we know, Albanian language has a lot of ambiguity words and that’s why Google translate may be confused on translating our language and that’s why we would encourage my students not to use it.

2.2 Using Google Translate to Learn a Language

A lot of people are interesting to learn new languages especially English since it considered to be the most important language in the world. Many people think that learning English would provide them with a better job, they could travel easily in other places because everywhere you go even if it is not an English place everybody knows a bit of it to talk and understand one another and so on. But nowadays the technology is on its peak and so is Google translate. From the abovementioned we saw that Google translate has improved a lot and is going to improve more and more in the future, but we still do not know if it is appropriate for learning a language. We believe that no teacher would agree with this, so are We. We would not recommend to anyone learning a language using Google translate just because from this research we saw many drawbacks of it. As we know GT is a machine and it could not give you grammar explanations or for any ambiguity word GT cannot provide you with such explanations, and that’s why everyone should learn the new language from books or with the help of a teacher.

According to Swedish made easy (2018) there are five reasons to avoid Google translate when learning a language:

- Google translate is a blunt tool;
- You can't trick anyone (at least not your teacher);
- No learning;
- Learning from mistakes is essential learning;
- Your writing is your reward ("Swedish-made-easy", 2018)

They gave explanations on each of them to demonstrate why we should avoid Google translate to learn a language.

1. Google Translate is a blunt tool

"Translation from one language to another is not simply about translating word for word ('direct method'). You need to also translate according to grammatical, idiomatic and cultural patterns, which may mean that a sentence might look quite different in terms of the actual words, but mean the same thing. Google translate stops your progress even if you don't notice at first".

2. You can't trick anyone (at least not your teacher!)

"A teacher's job is to know their subject, but it's also to know their student. They identify the student's level, where they're going and how to help them reach the finishing line".

3. No learning

"To learn anything from the beginning is an uphill struggle against waning willpower and outside influences. Don't let Google translate be part of that negative influence. Use real dictionary, if you must".

4. Learning from mistakes is essential learning

"In learning, mistakes are the key ingredients to understanding what is correct. Google translate doesn't teach you the nuances of language. A particular sentence can be written in different ways, depending on context, and that is what your teacher will show".

5. Your writing is your reward

"The feeling of personal satisfaction is more than ample reward for all the sweating, flicking through pages and trying to make sense of something you previously knew nothing about". (Swedish-made-easy, 2018)

So that is what the Swedish made easy tried to say. Teachers are those who can reward you for all that work you do on learning a new language and not the Google translate.

On the other hand Luca Lampariello points out that Google translate can be a very helpful tool in learning a new language (Lampariello, n.d.). According to him anyone who wants to learn a new language should follow these steps in order to have better translations from Google translate (Lampariello, n.d.). Here are the steps as follows with their explanations for each of them:

- ***Never Translate Single Words***

This is more of a recommendation than a strategy, but if you follow it, the quality of the translations you receive from Google Translate will be much, much better.

When you use Google Translate, never, ever use it to translate single words!

So again, please remember to **always use multiple word phrases or sentences when you input language into Google Translate**. It's the only way to ensure even a reasonably accurate translation.

- ***Create Instant, Bilingual Texts with Audio***

Why is it useful for Google Translate to be able to translate entire documents at a time? Because this means we can use it to **create** bilingual texts with audio (affiliate), all in a moment's notice.

How do you do this?

First you need a text in your target language. You should always start with an authentic target language text (affiliate), so that you are not learning from incorrect or inaccurate language.

- *Translate simple texts*

To get as accurate a translation as possible, you should stick to simple texts, like the ones normally written for the benefit of beginner and intermediate language learners.

- *Translate between "close" languages*

Languages that are "genetically" related usually share the same syntax, so if you are using two languages from the same language family (or even a larger grouping), your ultimate translation will be much better.

- ***Prepare Yourself for a Target Language Conversation***

Another engaging and smart way to use Google Translate is to use it to prepare speaking sessions with your tutor or language partner. When you have scheduled time for a conversation, be sure to spend at least twenty minutes beforehand preparing yourself. You can do this by using Google Translate to research words and phrases that will be useful in your upcoming conversation (Lampariello, n.d.).

Even that Luca Lampariello (n.d.) gives all these examples on how to properly use the Google translate in order to learn a new language he confirms that, “Google Translate translations are often decently accurate, but not accurate enough to be considered perfect, or at least equal to what a human translator would give you”, (Lampariello, n.d.). Furthermore he concludes that for language learning, Google Translate is neither a blessing, nor a curse. Rather, it is just a tool that when used correctly, can help you quickly find decent-quality translations between two languages. You can use it to create bilingual comprehensible texts (affiliate), to prepare conversations and use it on the fly to help you find words and expressions you don't know or still can't use.

All in all, we think Google Translate is a great tool. It is free, easy to use and intuitive in most situations. It does have its limitations, of course (especially for certain combinations of languages) but the overall quality of the translations is constantly improving.

In any case, we think it is best used by beginner or low-intermediate learners, and with combinations of languages that share a similar syntax (Lampariello, n.d.).

2.2.1 How to use Google Translate to teach English?

Being a teacher of a second language sometimes is a bit frustrating. From the teachers' experiences they realized that every student is aware of Google translate and as a result of it they use it a lot. According to them the students are shy or they just do not want to cooperate with the teacher for their homework or their translated text. So they use it for their homework they are in touch with the internet too and of course the language used is English so they are a bit 'forced' to use Google translate. According to Beare (2018) we as teachers can use Google translate in order to explain something easily and not to lose much time on trying to explain it in English (Beare, 2018). He gives an example as if a teacher teaches in a Spanish class but the teacher does not speak Spanish at all, and there the teacher should explain Present Perfect and uses a lot of different examples to make them understand but it is hard to do it and here Beare (2018) propose to use Google translate in order to save time and explain it in a minute and then again keep explaining in English(Beare, 2018).

He also gives an example how to do it properly:

- Have students write short texts in English, and translate them into their original language. Using Google Translate for translation can help students catch grammatical errors by spotting these errors in the translations.
- Use authentic resources, but provide the URL and have students translate the original into their target language. This will help out when it comes to difficult vocabulary. Make sure that students use Google Translate only after they have first read the article in English.
- For beginners, ask students to first write short texts in their mother tongue. Have them translate into English and ask them to tweak the translation.

- Provide your own short text and let Google Translate into the class' target language(s). Ask students to read the translation and then try to come up with the English original text.
- If all else fails, use Google Translate as a bilingual dictionary (Beare, 2018).

So according to Kenneth Beare (2018), it is not a bad thing if we make our classes easier and use a bit of Google translate. As he explained we should teach our students how to use GT in order not to let them being misled by using it in a wrong way.

2.3 To use or not to use Google Translate in English language

There is a huge gap on this topic. From the things mentioned above we saw that Google translate is very popular and almost every person uses it for his/her personal purposes. So to answer the question to use or not to use Google translate in English learning is a bit hard to give the proper answer.

According to Fitrotul Maulidiyah (2018) in order to avoid the excessive use of machine translations, EFL learners must be further supervised on how to wisely and accountably use this machine translation so that in the future, it would not ruin their products of translation. As we know that Google translate has its own benefits and drawbacks according to him the learners should be supervised if the Google translate is used in the classroom (Maulidiyah, 2018).

On the other hand, a research made in the Saudi Arabia about the use of Google translates in their learning in the University showed that, “there is a need for a framework that addresses the pedagogical implications of GT use. Only very low percentages of the students reported having received any training on the use of GT. This kind of training is not incorporated into FL teaching methods courses, which is a serious oversight given the frequency with which students use GT to support their language learning. Instructors should familiarize themselves with the intended purposes, features, strengths and weaknesses of GT so that they are better equipped to it. Taking into consideration student behaviors and views, such as those presented in this study, instructors should determine the kinds of GT use they will prohibit or allow in a given class, or even for certain types of assignments. They should clearly articulate rules and consequences to their students, both in course syllabi and during in-class discussions” (Eid Alhaisoni & Maha Alhaysony, 2017).

So according to them even if the students know the benefits and the drawbacks of using Google translate they still use it for specific purposes. In this case no one can stop them from using it and they propose to make a list of do's and don'ts in order to assess properly the works of the students. In this way the students are aware for the limitations of Google translate use in their works that have to be assessed from the professors (Eid Alhaisoni & Maha Alhaysony, 2017).

The researcher personally agrees with their work, and this is something that we would like to do with my students. In the beginning of the year there would be a scale in which the students

would exactly know how far can go in the usage of Google translate. And also the assessment of their works would also be easy.

2.3.1 Pro's and Con's of using Google Translate

Every single application has its pros and cons so does Google translate. The authors of Language connections (n.d.) show us pros and cons of using Google translate which according to them the way that Google Translate works is that it uses frequency of word pairs between two languages as a database for its translations. Although this works well in some cases, often this means that it cannot put a translation into proper context without the help of a human. In fact, it may in some circumstances come up with outright errors or extremely awkward literal translations (Languageconnections, n.d.)

They list pros and cons in this way:

THE PROS

1. *Google Translate is free.* An experienced professional translator can sometimes be costly, but remember you get what you pay for.
2. *Google Translate is quick.* One of the main advantages of Google Translate is that it is very fast. In fact, a human translator(s) cannot compete with the speed nor, as a result, the quantity of translations that Google Translate is able to perform. In an average workday an experienced translator can translate about 2,000 words maximum (300-400 words/hour) depending on the difficulty of the text. In contrast, Google Translate is able to produce a translation with the same number of words in just seconds!
3. *Google Translate uses a statistical method to form an online translation database based on language pair frequency.* Google Translate uses a statistical approach to build an online database for translations that are often (**but not always**) produced by humans and are available online.

THE CONS

With Google Translate the meaning can be “lost in translation” because there is no way to incorporate context. *The complexity of the text, as well as any context which cannot be interpreted without a true knowledge of the language, makes the likelihood of errors greater. Direct translation is common with Google Translate and often results in nonsensical literal translations while professional translators take great pains to ensure that this does not happen by using well-established online glossaries, back translation methods, proof readers and reviewers.*

1. *The quality of translation is dependent on the language pair.* Which source and target languages are involved also affects the quality of the translation. Since Google’s web-based translation database is built primarily from existing online translations, common

- translations for languages e.g. Spanish or English tend to be more accurate while translations for other languages that are not as available in Google's database are less likely to be accurate.
2. *Google Translate often produces translations that contain significant grammatical errors.* This is due to the fact that Google's translation system uses a method based on language pair frequency that does not take into account grammatical rules.
 3. *Google Translate does not have a system to correct for translation errors.* There is no way of reporting errors in order to avoid having them repeated, nor is there a way to proof read what has been translated unless one is fluent in both the source and the target language.

The researcher personally agrees with this research because we know these things also from my experience and saw these pros and cons by testing Google translate and that's why we do not recommend that much my students to use it because if they continue using Google translate without the help of a teacher it can mislead them on their way of learning English language. We also do agree that technology is evolving day by day but that does not mean that human mind isn't and that's why students should keep this in mind and keep learning more from books and dictionaries rather than Google translate. They should find middle between these two.

There is a lot of researching about pros and cons of Google translate and here according to Silver Bay Translations editors the pros of using Google translate are that "Google Translate is extremely fast. It is so fast that no human translator can hope to compete with it at all. A human translator might translate 4,000 words in an 8-10 hour day. But Google Translate can do that in an instant. Google Translate is also free. Google's translate is absolutely zero cost to its users. Google Translate uses many (but not all) translations obtained from human translations already online" (Silver Bay Translations", 2019).

As it has its pros Google translate has also its cons of using and according to the editors of Silver Bay Translations Google Translate is known to make many errors. The quality of Google Translate varies from language pair to language pair. It can be suitable for language pairs such as English-to-Spanish translation or other highly common languages if you have some linguistic knowledge of them but a user has no way of knowing whether Google's German translation of an English text is any good. Simply getting a result—any result—in no way guarantees that the result is good. There is no privacy with Google Translate. For instance, when you upload your text to Google Translate, you're might as well say saying, "Here Google! You can have all of my private information to store, ("Silver Bay Translations", 2019). So they aware us to be careful with the use of Google translate.

2.3.2 Reasons to avoid Google Translate

Google translate is a machine translator which translates whatever you write there. Many people use it for various purposes but we still do not have the idea if it is that good to use it or to avoid it. Many researchers say that you can use Google translate to translate only word by word but if you need to translate a whole text then you should seek for a professional translator. Here

according to Twose (2019) if you are travelling and need to understand the menu in a foreign language then Google Translate can be a lifesaver, but it's a different situation when your clients need to translate important "confidential or creative documents, which will involve subtle nuances and a good understanding of the source language". If the materials involve "legal contracts, financial reports, compliance training materials, health-related documents, pharmaceutical drug trials or global branding videos", Google Translate is unlikely to be the right tool for your business and it also can be risky because Google translate registers every word written in it (Twose, 2019).

Twose (2019) made a research and here she lists 6 reasons to avoid using the Google translate:

1. "Machine translation does save time and reduces costs, but free translation platforms are not ideal when important and confidential documents are involved. Some companies have found that their confidential data was published online after they had used online translation tools to translate company data.
2. Bugs can happen with machine learning and machine translation tools. GT now uses a combination of machine learning and the help of human volunteers to make sure translations are more accurate, but it's still **far from perfect**.
3. As the Guardian points out, if the English version of The Girl from Ipanema had been Google Translated, Frank Sinatra would be singing "*Girl in the golden body, sun from Ipanema, the it swung its more than a poem*", which clearly doesn't make much sense. Literature, music, and poetry are not under immediate threat due to the nuances needed to convey the original ideas when translating, which GT still doesn't grasp.
4. Back translations are not a guaranteed way of checking if the content has been translated accurately.
5. To use GT, you need to be connected to the internet at all times.
6. Interpreters can't use it because they would have to type everything people said in meetings and conferences into the tool to be able to provide a translation. It would be too time-consuming, inefficient, and inaccurate" (Twose, 2019).

As we know that Google translate is a machine that means that it cannot translate well the ambiguity words and a lot of languages have a lot of ambiguity words and that's why you need a dictionary or the help of a professional translator if we have to translate something of a big importance. On the other hand another researcher tells us to avoid Google translate as he says "Problem: too many students use Google translate when studying, during class, when doing homework. Sure, Google translate is convenient, but depending on the context not always exact far from the ideal study tool", ("3 Reasons to avoid GT", 2019). Here is the list of 3 reasons to avoid the using of Google translate according to the author of 3 Reasons to avoid GT (2019):

It's not a study or resource tool

"Google translate is a translation software developed for basic translations. It's not developed or conceived as a study tool, so better not use it as such".

There's no why

According to 3 Reasons to avoid GT (2019), dictionaries work the best, but he thinks that students don't know how to use them properly and that's why they fall back on GT instead. He confirms that GT translates very basic words, but when it gets more abstract then it doesn't translate efficiently and also doesn't learn us the meaning of the word, if it is a noun, an adjective and so on and in the end as he says, "better to get used to the concept of a dictionary from the beginning" ("3 Reasons to avoid GT", 2019).

The problems of context-based translation...

"Google translate might be relatively accurate when it comes to translating sentences. Sure, that might be convenient for you but it ultimately won't help you very much when it comes to using the language independently. It does all the work for you". He continues by giving an example on how GT works. Here is the example: the Portuguese verb "*ficar*" which depending on the context or usage can mean "to stay", "to be located in", "to become" or "to be situated in". There's no way that Google translate could ever convey the different meanings and contexts of this individual word. That's because it relies on the context to give you the correct translation ("3 Reasons to avoid GT", 2019).

So, it seems that Google translate is not a good tool even for businesses nor for the students. It would not be good if the students rely on Google translate for their homework. It should be avoided unless it is used as a pedagogical tool from the teachers in order to facilitate the class and save time. From the teachers' experiences we can say that Google translate can facilitate and save us time but in the other hand students can be depended on it and they would not think out of the box or critically. So that's why teachers should teach their learners to avoid it at home and not to use it that much in their classes in order to save time because in this way the students could become lazy.

2.4 Google Translate in EFL Classroom taboo or teaching tool?

Teachers say that they do not have laptops in their schools and they cannot use the technology. Since the policy of the schools doesn't allow students to use their phones as a learning tool and the school by itself cannot provide anyone with laptops we might suppose that Google translate cannot be used by them only by the teachers. And since Google translate can be downloaded in laptops or IOS they can use it if they see it appropriate in teaching. We personally use it sometimes in my classes and let my students know how it works and how should they work on it whenever they need the help of GT. So for me as a teacher it is not a taboo but it can be a teaching tool if we work properly. So if Google translate is used in classroom with the help of the teacher it can be a useful tip for them. As Stannard (2018) a teacher training videos points out that Google Translate can be very helpful to learn new vocabulary and it also helps them saving the words or phrases in many forms in their computers and also can print what they learn. So according to him Google translate can be a teaching tool in learning a new language.

Furthermore he shows tips on how the teachers should use it by saying that “teachers can use Google translate to test their learners or the learners can test each other about their knowledge”, (Stannard, 2018). He adds that if you are signed into “Google or Gmail account then you can copy your vocabulary list or lexical sets into a Google sheet”. As the things mentioned above were pro of using GT as a learning tool this can only be like that in a positive way if teachers use it in the classroom together with their students otherwise it can mislead the students if they use it at home for a long time.

Other researchers (Adriana Riess Karnal & Pereira W.Vera, 2013) about the use of Google translator as a tool in learning goes like this by showing us that “it is possible to use machine translation to both partially comprehend texts and use it to enhance knowledge in the English Reading lesson. That means Google translator can work as didactic material, that is, the translated text can work as linguistic input students must be attentive. What we mean is that the teacher who uses electronic translation in class can develop strategies so as to orient the reader to the errors the machine made or not. Finally, we would like to discuss how Google translator has been developed and how much the reader and teachers can use it as a tool to teach or learn. We should teach our students to be independent of any translator while they are reading; however, electronic tools can be helpful to make students linguistically aware while they are in the process of learning. In the future we will probably see more accurate electronic translators” (Adriana Riess Karnal & Pereira W.Vera, 2013).

So according to these researchers, technology is something that it is going to be among us in anytime so teachers should find a balance in how to incorporate the GT in this case into our classes. Since we know that the students use GT, we as teachers should show them the path on how to use it properly, to make the difference of the GT translation and the human mind’s translation in order to find out the mistakes and in this way they would learn better.

2.4.1 Google translate for teachers

For an English speaker or in this case a teacher, Google translate can be a very helpful tool of teaching. As a teacher understands the language, the grammar, the pronunciation, a machine translation cannot fool him/her, but it can be risky for the students to use it since they are in the process of learning the language and they can learn some things in wrong way. According to Emanuelle Martin-Lacore (2020), “direct exposure to language in real-life contexts of communication represents an essential part of second language acquisition but will not promote effective learning without secure knowledge of essential linguistic rules”, (Lacore-Martin, 2020). And then Google translate happened and as she noted this machine came firstly as “service and went from laughably unreliable to infinitely more efficient or even artful in the most frequently used languages”. Furthermore she points out that this machine translation was becoming astonishingly reliable, and it was freely and easily accessible to all. “For us, this represented a

challenge to fair assessment that deeply impacted our teaching and learning environment” (Lacore-Martin, 2020).

It is true that this phenomenon affected the fair assessment and it is a very big challenge for us as teachers, so that’s why we must be aware of the translation that students make, in order to make a fair assessment on their work. As a student uses the GT also us teachers should use it in order to see what their work would be like in order to be fair with our students.

Google translate can be a very helpful tool if us as teachers would use it in our classrooms. Nowadays the technology is evolving, and so should us, and that’s why we have to be aware of any other tool that students might use to ease their work.

2.5 Benefits of Google Translate for students

Every application that we use has its benefits and a drawback, so also the Google translate has its own benefits for students if they use it properly. Nowadays almost every person has a smart phone so the first benefit of GT is that you can download it in your phone for free. Then the translation is only one click away. According to Abhijit Ahaskar (2016), there are 5 reasons why Google translate is better than any other translation tool and here is the list below:

- *Translates in more Indian languages;*
- *Provides voice feedback;*
- *Google can also translate web pages;*
- *Translate text messages;*
- *More than just the meaning (Ahaskar, 2016).*

Ahaskar (2016), contend that these reasons are not good only in learning e new language but also the students can use it wherever they go. It is a free app and it also works offline. So according to him Google translate works better than other machine translations as these features make it worthy to try (Ahaskar, 2016). In order to see the benefits and drawbacks of using Google translate in classroom (Valijärvi & Tarsoly, 2019) made a research for the Finnish and Hungarian language and used the Google translate in classroom to see if, “students become more critical, and more competent, users of online translation tools as well”. According to the research Google translate can be a learning tool but more for the advanced students than the beginners because the advanced ones can think critically if they see something wrong translated from the GT, and in the other hand it can mislead the beginners (Valijärvi & Tarsoly, 2019). According to them, “correcting and post-editing texts produced by *Google Translate*TM not only boosted students’ confidence in their own language ability but was also useful in directing their attention to detail and spotting mistakes”. Others (Mundt and Groves, 2016) argue that the availability of free machine translation, particularly Google Translate, leads to major transformations in both Higher Education and language learning.

2.5.1 What I learned when my students used Google Translate

There are some reasons according by the Spanish plans why students do use Google translate, especially in this pandemic time. “The problem is not new for language teachers, but without being able to have all writing done in the classroom during distance learning, the problem is now more relevant than ever”, (Spanishplans, 2020). They list three reasons about the usage of Google translate and these are as follows:

- **Laziness:** they don't want to think about what they've learned and what they already know how to say in the target language. They just want to get the assignment done and translators have the answers they are looking for.
- **Frustration:** Students want to be able to express themselves with the same language ability as they are accustomed to in their native language. Students are likely thinking about how to answer the question in their native language and are translating word by word and when they come across a word (or sentences) they don't know, they look it up.
- **Relevance/Compliance:** Students aren't concerned about language acquisition and just want to get a good grade. They want to please their teacher and think that the answer is more important than the method. They may not even be interested in learning the language, are just required to take the class to get credit (Spanishplans, 2020).

They pointed out some really good reasons and we agree for most of them, but we as teachers should not give up and we still should be our students' heroes in their learning. We know that the students also want to get good grades in order to please their teachers or their parents but this is not the way. We as teachers should show them the right path and make them believe in themselves and not to a machine translation.

2.5.2 Friend or Foe?

Several studies agree that Google translate can be also a friend in learning a new language but does it really help them or it is just a foe. As (Groves & Mundt, 2014) noted, with a recent development in digital technology, machine translation (MT), is improving in its ability to translate with grammatical and lexical accuracy, and is also becoming increasingly available for students of language for academic purposes.

“Google Translate is no longer the crude tool that it used to be”, (Davies, 2011). As he says, “Let's face it, automatic translation tools have been around for a long time and that are here to stay”, (Davies, 2011).

So, to the question friend or foe, according to Graham Davies (2011), he is “in no doubt that most students would just accept what Google Translate offers as the first choice and hope for the best. But a clever student would investigate Google Translate's new features and produce quite an acceptable translation that does not have the obvious hallmark of being translated by machine”.

This makes us believe that in what way Google translate is used, that it can be also a friend but also a foe. On the other hand according to Amanda Soo, if you are a translator worrying about

your relevance in the age of AI-takeover, fret not. Instead of seeing technology as the enemy threatening to rob you of your livelihood, you should see it as an assistant that helps you excel at your job (Soo, 2020).

So obviously Google translate can be a friend to those who know a language well but it can be a foe for the beginners who think that they may learn a new language by using Google translate.

3. The Purposes of the study

The purpose of this study is to see the assessment of the texts translated by Google translate in four schools in Suhareka and Malisheva municipalities. There will also be discussions with the teachers if they believe that Google translate can be a pedagogical tool or should be avoided at all. The aim of the study is if Google translate is used more in primary or secondary schools and also to see the reasons for what they use it more. How they react to the Google translated texts and if they give to their students lower grades in their assignments. Another purpose is to see if experienced teachers give more assignments or those of inexperienced. Since Google translate is a world wide web and is a very famous app in the world, it is also used in Kosova, so this research would tell us more about its usage in primary and secondary schools.

3.1 Research questions

This study aims to answer these questions:

1. How do the teachers grade the Google translated texts in primary and secondary schools?
2. What are teachers' reactions when reading GT's from students?
3. Do teachers believe GT has a role as a pedagogical tool or should be avoided in the classroom?
4. Is Google translate accurate in translating from English-Albanian and vice-versa?

3.2 Research hypothesis

This research will ascertain the following hypothesis:

1. Google translate has a very big impact at schools
2. Students of secondary schools use Google translate more than those of the primary schools
3. Google translate represented as a challenge to fair assessment.

4. Research design and methodology

For this specific thesis the following method has been used:

- Comparative method (between primary and secondary schools)
- Observation / Participant Observation (Teachers of primary and secondary schools)
- Surveys (for teachers and students)
- Texts to translate by students (8th and 10th graders)
- Interviews (with teachers of primary and secondary schools)

4.1 Data gathering procedure

A variety of methods were used to gather information for my research. Besides the questionnaires there were also the discussion and observation in primary and secondary schools in Suhareka and Malisheva municipalities. There were 4 schools from both places, where two of them were from Suhareka, one was a primary and the other was a secondary school and the same were in Malisheva. The questionnaires were shared online for teachers and the students, whereas the texts were shared to the students of these schools but the students were not obliged to translate those texts, only those who wanted to be part of the study. The students didn't know the purpose of the study so they had just to translate those texts given to them and then their teachers should check them. They given time to complete the task was 3 days and then they should have given them to their teachers. The discussion was made with the teachers during their checking of students' task. Also the questionnaires for the teachers were shared in the same way. The research or the statements made on this research were about the usage of Google translate, how the teachers grade the Google translates texts, their reactions about it, if the teachers approve the usage of Google translate and if they give instructions on how to use it and would they incorporate the online translation sources in their teaching. On the other hand the statements for the students were if they use it, in what way they use it, so if they translate only words or whole texts. After the administration of the questionnaires, the results obtained from the participants were analyzed and the data was presented in tables. In the other hand the teachers of the schools we chose to make my research were asked to check the translated texts by their students, because they know them better and of course they would know better which students used Google translate to complete the task. And the discussion made with the teachers was based in the questionnaires and these translated texts by their students.

4.2 Participants

The participants of my study were 4 schools, where 2 of them were from Suhareka and 2 of them were from Malisheva. There were 2 primary and 2 secondary schools.

There were also 80 teachers who completed the questionnaires online and 150 students who also completed the questionnaires online and they were from different villages and different cities from all over the Kosovo. The students of the schools in my study didn't have to complete the questionnaires.

4.2.1 Teacher participants

There were 8 teachers from all the schools, so 2 teachers per school. They answered 10 questions of the questionnaire. Besides the teachers of these schools, there were a lot more from the questionnaires completed online and they were from a lot of places in Kosovo. There were 80 questionnaires completed online where 13 teachers were from Suhareka, 14 from Malisheva, 13 from Prizren, 8 from Prishtina, 7 from Gjakova, 4 from Peja, 3 from Gjilan, 3 from Fushe Kosove, 2 from Mitrovica and 1 from Lipjan, Ankara(Turkey), Dragash, Hani Elezit, North Macedoina, Viti and Vushtrri. So the questionnaires took place in a lot of places and in this way the research would be more completed with their given answers on my topic. The teachers were mostly from primary school and there were teachers of different ages who took part in my questionnaires.

4.2.2 Student participants

150 students from different schools and places were part of my study. They answered 10 questions of the questionnaire. The questionnaires were shared online, so different students of different places in Kosovo were part of my study too. The students of the 4 schools had to translate texts and not to complete the questionnaires. The number of the students that took part was not that high because the students chose if they wanted to be a part of the study or not. So there were 12 students from the secondary school in Suhareka, 8 of them from Malisheva. From the primary schools, there were 17 students from Suhareka and 14 from Malisheva.

4.3 Materials

To have better results of my research I used a lot of materials, mostly from the internet like books, online researches, journals, questionnaires, observation and discussion with the teachers. There were also two texts chosen from the internet adapted to the ages of the primary and secondary schools. So the texts were adapted for the 8th graders and the 10th graders as well. The students should have to complete their task without knowing the purpose of my study.

4.4. Procedures

This research was divided into five main phases and each phase will be described as follows:

1. *The first phase* includes part were more reading regarding chosen topic were done.
2. *The second phase*, is where participants and questions for the questionnaires were defined.
3. *The third phase* includes the checking of the texts and the assessment of the teachers toward their students in the given texts by me.
4. *The fourth phase* includes teachers interviewing and statistical data analysis as well.
5. *The fifth phase* includes the part where the writing up was done.

4.5 Instruments

Questionnaires were prepared and applied in four different schools in Suhareka and Malisheva and also online. Each questionnaire was composed of ten questions.

In the first part of the questionnaire participants were informed about the purpose of taking the questionnaire.

In the second part they were asked to fill in the questions regarding their opinion. Besides the questionnaires there were also two texts adapted to their age. So one text was adapted for the 10th graders and the other one was adapted for the 8th graders.

4.6 Interpretation of Findings/Results

In the following are presented the findings in charts regarding to the questions in the questionnaires and the discussion with the teachers. Firstly I will present the findings from the questionnaires for the teachers. The completed questionnaires were mostly online so there are 80 questionnaires and the teachers are from all over the Kosovo. In the part of the participants we mentioned where the teachers were from. So this research aimed to find out how the teachers assess the Google translated texts, in primary and secondary schools, what are their reactions towards the Google translated texts, if they use it personally or if they advise their students to use it for their homework. The research will also tell us about the advantages and disadvantages that teachers think how the Google translate could lead or mislead their students in learning English language and a lot of other things that we will present in diagrams, charts and tables to see them better. The questionnaires were completed by the primary and secondary schools, but there were also some questionnaires completed by 4 teachers that work in private courses, 2 of them in universities, 7 of them in secondary schools and 67 questionnaires were completed by the primary school teachers.

Chart 1. Pre-question – Teachers' questionnaires

So the majority of teachers, 84% were from primary schools. Most of the teachers have a lot of experience in teaching whether they work in primary or secondary schools, but even if they have a lot of experience in their teaching, from the discussion made with the teachers from Suhareka and Malisheva they do accepted that Google translate is now a phenomenon that is happening in our schools and we cannot do much about that since every student now has a Smartphone and the access to Google translate is one click away. Since we know that Google translate now is a part of our schools we wanted to know if the teachers advise or not their students to use it in a proper way. The questionnaires were completed from a very large number of experienced teachers and we were interested to know what they think about it. According to this table we see that even that there are a lot of experienced teachers they are still divided into categories of yes and no answers. So half of the experienced teachers said that they advise their pupils how to use it in order to have better result of using it and the other half said that they do not advise their pupils how to do it.

Teachers that advise and don't advise their students how to use Google translate based on their teaching experience	
No	27
1 year	1
Primary school	1
10 years	1
Primary school	1
11 years	3
High school	1
Primary school	2
12 years	1
High school	1
13 years	1
High school	1
14 years	1
High school	1
15 years	1
Primary school	1
17 years	1
Primary school	1
19 years	2
Primary school	2
2 years	2
English Course	2
20 years	1
English Course	1
20 years	1
Primary school	1
21 years	1
Primary school	1
22 years	1
Primary school	1
26 years	1
Primary school	1
3 years	1

Primary school		1
30 years		1
Primary school		1
4 years		1
Primary school		1
5 years		2
English Course		1
High school		1
7 years Primary school	1	
8 years		1
Primary school		1
9 years		1
University		1
Yes		53
1 year		2
Primary school		2
10 years		8
High school		1
Primary school		7
11 years		2
Primary school		2
12 years		2
Primary school		2
14 years		4
Primary school		4
15 years		2
Primary school		2
17 years		1
Primary school		1
18 years		1
Primary school		1
19 years		1
Primary school		1
19 years		1
Primary school		1
2 years		2
Primary school		2
2 years		1
Primary school		1
20 years		4
Primary school		4
21 years Primary school		2
22 years Primary school		1
24 years		1
Primary school		1
25 years		2

Primary school	2
26 years	1
Primary school	1
28 years	1
Primary school	1
29 years	1
Primary school	1
38 years	1
Primary school	1
5 years	4
Primary school	4
6 years	2
High school	1
Primary school	1
7 years	3
Primary school	2
University	1
8 years	3
Primary school	3
Grand Total	80

Table 1. Question 1. Teachers' questionnaire based on their age, teaching experience and the place of work

Based on this table we can see that even there are teachers with a lot of years experience they advise their students how to use Google translate, but in the other hand there are other teachers who share the years of experience but do not advise their students to use it. So we cannot say that teachers who are more experienced advise or don't advise on this point but this has to do with their type of teachers, their trainings or other stuff that affect them on how behave according to Google translate.

An experienced teacher that works in the secondary school in Malisheva Sh.Th. said that the students in their school use a lot the Google translate for specific purposes and the school doesn't have a policy to not use it at all but this came to be a challenge for us as teachers and to make a fair assessment it would be very hard. As we mentioned above in the literature review we saw that in the beginning of launch Google translate was only a machine translation but it is improving very fast and now translates very similarly as a human brain, especially for some language pairs. The same thing said Lacore-Martin from the literature review in chapter two where she said "that the use of Google translate by students represents a challenge to fair assessment that deeply impacts our teaching and learning environment". Another teacher S.S from a primary school in Suhareka said that students in her school also use Google translate but the only thing for her as a teacher is to say to them not to use it that much and give advises to them if they do not stop using it because she doesn't have any other thing to do in that case. From the discussion in the other school in Suhareka the teacher A.SH said the Google translate now is known from every student and its usage is at very high use. He said that he can see at his students' work when they have to translate something at home. And also we as teachers know every student of ours and of course we know their work at class and when they bring the homework we can understand that

they did not do it by themselves. He said that he cannot do much but lead them how to use in better way in order not to use it that much because it can mislead their learning and they do not benefit anything by using it all the time. We also talked about the reasons why the students use it and according to him the students nowadays are a bit lazy in classes and do not ask many questions during the class and their age is also fragile where he took an example about it. If a student ask a question about a word for example and the others know that word they laugh on that student and this makes it hard for him/her, and in this way students start to make less questions during the class, so he thinks that bullying can be a reason why the students do not take the advantage to talk and that's why they lay to another form of learning and not the teacher.

So about the question if teachers advise their students to use the Google translate, 53 teachers said yes they do advise their students to use the Google translate and 27 of them said no. In the following question if they advise them, we asked them if they give instructions on how to use it and the answers were like this where 53 of 57 said yes, the others said no or they left that part blank. So from this report we can see that Google translate is so among us and we as teachers should better advise them to use it rather than forcing them to avoid it because we cannot control our students all the time if they are using it or not. Google translate can mislead the students if they use it without our help, but if we are close to our students and talk about their misunderstandings during the classes or any unknown word, we think that we could manage the situation better than neglecting it.

The diagram tells us better in percentages how many of the teachers from secondary and primary schools advise their students on how to use it.

Chart 2. Question 1. Teachers' questionnaire

Chart 3. Question 1.1 Teachers' questionnaire

As teachers give advises on how to use Google translate they answered to the question in what cases is it okay to use it, and their answers differs from one another but most of them said that the students should use Google translate when they have any unknown words and they do not have any dictionary and have no choice but using it. All of them said that the students should not use the GT to translate the whole text because it can increase their desire on learning something new, so they shouldn't rely always on it but they should memorize the new words that they learn during their classes. Some teachers said that the students should use it only for orientation or when they forget a word that they learned it earlier so they can use it to recall it. From their experience on using the GT they know that it is not that accurate on translating in our language so that's why the teachers are a bit skeptical on letting their students rely that much on it. So about its accuracy in our questionnaires were asked the teachers for advantages and disadvantages of using Google translate. Most of the teachers said that Google translate have a lot of advantages. Some of them said that they have experience with GT and they know that it is fast to use, it is simple, you can use it offline once you download it in your phone. They also add that Google translate has improved a lot and it gives you additional information about the word that you translate as pronunciation of the word, semantics, a lot of examples where you can use it, it saves the history of words that you used once. As Language wire authors and Makvana said in the chapter two about the advantages of Google translate that is a free application, you can use it offline and is a very fast application, but another researcher Nick McGuire talks about its accuracy and says that if you translate an entire page, you'll notice it gets the general message across, but is still far from perfect. In the other hand some teachers said that they do not recommend it at all and one of them said that there is no advantage neither for teachers nor for students and in that case according to him Google translate has not any advantage at all. So the teachers answered to the question if they see any disadvantage in using GT and according to most of them GT has a lot of disadvantages.

The researcher will mention some of a more importance. Most of the teachers said that students should not use the GT to translate whole texts because it does not have accuracy in it. Since our language has a lot of ambiguity words, that would affect in their accurate translation.

Same as Tzounis described GT as a machine translation and he said that when it comes to translate the ambiguity words or the meaning depend on the syntax this is where the famous Google translate falls short compared to a professional translator. As it was seen from the research GT translates better depending on the pair languages, and unfortunately our language doesn't take part on these languages. Teachers said that GT is not accurate in translating whole texts so that can be as disadvantages of Google translate against our language. Another researcher Lampariello said that GT translates better when the languages share similar syntax. Some other teachers said that the students can be addicted to the use of Google translate and that would make the students lazy on learning because they would always rely on the easiest way. Even it can be helpful for the advanced students it can be very tricky for the beginners and it could mislead them in learning the language. Another teacher said that there is risks of using Google translate especially when students find comfort in completing their tasks without learning the very same words they have been searching.

So as we understood from the researchers and the teachers' questionnaires, there are a lot of advantages and disadvantages of using Google translate. Since we learned that Google translate can mislead the beginners it means that the advanced students and we as teachers can use GT sometimes when we need it. Also a researcher Kenneth Beare said that we as teachers can use GT to ease our class in proper cases, or when we have to explain something easily not to lose much time. So about time was one of the advantages that teachers claimed where they said that using Google Translate may save time when you are short of it instead of using a dictionary. Google translate has improved a lot since its first launch and now it does not only translate words but it also gives grammar explanation, different examples of the word by using it in sentences so this makes a bit hard the fair assessment by the teachers. So to know more about it on that how the teachers react towards the Google translated text and how they assess them they answered the questions about it. So another question for the teachers was how they proceed when they see that a student used Google translate. And some of them said that they do not mind it and there is nothing wrong with using Google Translate but they also ask them questions about the translated text. Another teacher said that he asks them to do it again and guide them in using it wisely, and then help them understand that it is a mistake and compare the translation with the original one. Another one also said that he doesn't mind it but he encourages the students to use a dictionary instead. So according to the answers the teachers have accepted that Google translate is something not new for them and they get used of it because the students use it a lot, but they try to do their best to help their students to avoid its usage and to not rely always on it. And about the assessment of the Google translated texts most of the teachers said that they advise their students not to use it and they do not give lower grades toward a Google translated text, they said that they give suggestions on how to use properly GT and they also suggest to not use it at all.

One of the teachers said that he analyzes the text well and then puts a grade; another one said that he/she doesn't give texts to translate as homework. A lot of teachers said that they assess depending how much they used GT in their text. Some teachers said that they ask questions about the translated text if they doubt that the students used the Google translate but they do not mind if yes unless the student learned the words and linked them well in the text. Some of the teachers said that they do not assess the translated texts at all, they just go through it together to see the mistakes and how should they translate properly. The teachers appreciate the work that they do even if they use Google translate for their work. Besides the assessment the teachers were asked in the questionnaires if they give lower grades if they see that the student used Google translate to their texts. Most of them so 67 teachers said that they would not assess their students with lower grades, 12 of them said that yes they would give lower grades and one questionnaire was left blank. According to this question the teacher A.B. from the secondary school in Suhareka said that he doesn't give lower grades if he sees a Google translated text but he uses a scale for Google translated texts on that how much the student used it in the text. He said that he gives 100 points to a text and then when correcting it he puts minus points every time he doubts that the student used Google translate and also asks questions about those phrases or sentences and then suggests to the student what to do next and in this way the students are more aware on that what to do or not to do when they translate a text. So he said that he wants to help the students to be independent, to learn by themselves and not to be addicted always in Google translate because in that way they would be lazy and never learn how to translate a phrase, a sentence or a whole text.

Chart 4. Question 6.1 – Teachers' questionnaire

From the diagram we can also see the percentages of those who give and who do not give lower grades. As we see 70% of the primary teachers do not give lower grades and 14% of them give lower grades. Those of high school teachers are divided as follows where 8% of the teachers do not give lower grades and 5% of them do. So according to these results the majority of the teachers do not see as a bad influence the use of Google translate but as something helpful to the student, and not something that would be harmful for their learning.

According to the questionnaires most of the teachers give translations as a homework, but there is a part of them that think that teachers should not give translations as a homework because in this way students would use more the Google translate and according to them it is better to try together to translate at class. There were 50 teachers that give homework and 30 of them said no.

Chart 5. Question 9 – Teachers’ questionnaire

Those who give homework about translation are also divided into two groups where 27 of them give homework based on translation 1-2 times per month and 23 of them give homework 1-2 times per week, and divided into percentage based on the type of school that they teach, we can see that the majority of those who give homework are the primary teachers with 55%. The other part of the teachers said that they rarely give homework based on translation at home or they never give assignments like this at all. Here is the diagram that explains it better.

Chart 6. Question 9.1 Teachers' Questionnaire

As we saw abovementioned the teachers are aware, that the students use Google Translate even if they like it or not, so our job as teachers is to help them not to use it that much because we know that it could cost them in the future. The hardest job is for us as primary school teachers because that is the beginning of learning the English language so we can be their heroes and help them to learn the language without the help of other online sources until they are able to understand what are their advantages and disadvantages, so we as teachers should lead them in the proper way.

To see how the other teachers help their students to learn a new language through translation we asked them how they would help their pupils not to use Google translate for the whole text. The results show that the teachers play the role of a dictionary for their students in order to help them with the translation of any unknown word that they have.

Chart 7. Question 7 Teachers' Questionnaire

As we mentioned above, the teachers play the role of a dictionary and according to the results they mostly translate individual words for them, then some of them give definition of the new words in English, others translate groups of words and so on. Of course would be better to have dictionaries at schools for everyone but as the primary teacher R.B. from Suhareka said that this is kind of impossible. We know that the economy in Kosovo is not something to be proud of and since there are a lot of unemployed parents we as teachers cannot force them to provide their children with dictionaries. So that also may be a reason why the students use online sources such as Google translate. There may be a lot of reasons why is this happening but we as teachers have accepted that Google translate exists and we cannot do that much to avoid it. So since Google translate is among us and will be in the future we were interested to know from the teachers' perspective if they would incorporate translation applications in their teaching. From the discussion made another teacher from Malisheva B.B. said that Google translate or any other translation application are very easy to use nowadays and since our students have smart phones we recommend to them using it instead of a dictionary, because it is very hard to avoid it. From her experience, she said that the students used to bring her homework where they used Google translate and it was something that she couldn't do much, so she decided to let them use, to not forbidden it and advise them how to use and when to use it. According to her this method was better than to make them avoid it.

Chart 8. Question 8 Teachers' questionnaire

In this chart we can see that the answer, if the teachers would incorporate translation applications in their teaching is almost 50-50, so this means that some of the teachers are still skeptical about the usage of technology in their teaching. But as mentioned above, nowadays is very hard to avoid technology in our classrooms and Google translate is one of the applications. According to these answers, there are still a lot of teachers that do not see Google translate as a pedagogical tool and they do not use it in their teaching. These answers do not depend in their experience or their age because as we saw from this question in the questionnaire there were teachers who had a lot of experience in teaching and said that they use Google translate in their teaching but some other teachers also with a lot of experience in teaching said that they do not use it in their teaching so we cannot conclude something based on the experience of the teachers. Since there are a lot of teachers that would incorporate translation application in their teaching, they were also asked how would they do it, and the answers were mostly that they would advise their students how to use translation applications as Google translate or any other. One of the teachers said by encouraging them to translate individual words or sometimes groups of words so as not to lose the meaning of the sentence, another one said by talking for the machine translation, the history of translation, new methods or techniques and so on. Another opinion of a teacher is to have translation texts in the class from English into Albanian and vice versa and sometimes to use translated texts from translation application and let the student see for themselves what it looks like translating a human mind versus translation application. In general those who apply translation application said that they advise their students how to use it, some others said that they propose to use other translation application and not Google translate since they think that GT is not that accurate in translating English-Albanian and vice versa, and some others said that the students should use real dictionaries instead of online translation application. The last question in the teacher's questionnaire was about the use of Google Translate by the teachers themselves. As we saw from the earlier answers, we understood that also teachers use it since they know about it, they know how it works and of course from their experience they can advise their students how to use it properly. They also know its advantages and disadvantages but they are a bit forced to know

them since they have to make assessments and since the students nowadays use Google translate it is good for us as teachers to know more about Google translate and other online translation applications as well.

Chart 9. Question 10 Teachers' questionnaire

So, even if teachers do not recommend that much Google translate for their students, most of them use it personally when they have something unknown for them. In one way this is good because the teachers know how Google translate works and in this way is easier for them to make a fair assessment because they are able to know when a student used GT.

In the other hand we'll see how much the students use Google translate, for what they use it more, if their teachers help them to translate the text or they just give translation of the words, translation of the whole text or they just give it as a homework for them.

Most of the questionnaires were completed by the secondary school students so the results may not be so accurate to make the difference on that, which schools use it more or less.

Chart 10. Pre question – Students' Questionnaire

Students from primary and secondary schools completed the questionnaires in order to have a better view about the use of Google translate and to see the answers from the students perspective. In the following we are about to see a lot of information about GT, from the students' answers.

Another question from the students' questionnaire is if the teachers help their students to translate in the class or they do not translate in the class at all, because as we saw earlier in the teachers' answers, some of the teachers do not even give translation as a part of homework.

From the teachers' perspective we claimed that the students use a lot Google translate as they checked their homework they understood from that, but they also asked their students if they use it and the students' answers are positive on that question made toward them. To see a more clear answer if the students use it or not, this chart tells us better.

Chart 11. Prequestion – Students's Questionnaire

According to this question we can see that 66% of the secondary school students use Google translate and 25% of the primary school students. The other part of the students said that they do not use it. It can be that those are good students who do not need it that much because they can rely on their teachers and they are good learners. To understand it clearer we will see the answers of the students according to the question if their teachers help them to translate in class or not. As follows in this chart we can see that in a large percentage teachers help their students to translate in class which means that the students do not need that much to use Google translate or other translation applications to help them translate. So 58% of the secondary school said that their teachers help them to translate in class, so they can benefit a lot from it. In the other hand 20% of the primary school students claimed the same answer and the other part of the students which is not a large number tells us that the teachers do not help them to translate in the class. Those students who do not have the teachers' help, those tend more to use other sources in order to complete their tasks. And according to the teachers' answers we saw that large number of the students use Google translate but the majority of them do not give lower grades about it.

Chart 12. Question 1 – Students' questionnaire

We as teachers of course have a syllabus to complete during the school year and we know that there isn't that much space given to the translation part, so maybe that's why some of the teachers said that we do not give translations as homework but some of them said yes. Translation is a very important part of English language since we know that every new lesson, every new exercise has something new there and of course the students should know it in their mother tongue in order to understand it what is it about, even if we as teachers are supposed to talk only English during our classes. Besides that we are forced sometimes to use mother tongue for many reasons. One of them is translation, explaining something faster in order to save time and so on. That's why we as teachers should give homework even if it is about translation. The following question of the students' questionnaire is to see if the teachers say to their students to translate at home. According to this chart we see that secondary school teachers say to their students to translate at home. Maybe that's the main reason why most of them use Google translate. The percentage is high with 52% of them, where in the other hand 22% of the primary school students said that their teachers also say to them to translate at home which for my opinion is not a very good choice, because in this way we would produce more Google translate users. In the other hand, the syllabus in primary and secondary schools might be harder to complete and that's why the teachers give translation as homework.

We think we as teachers should take a step forward in order to help our students to be good translators because in this way they tend to understand better any task given to them to complete.

Chart 13. Question 2. Students' Questionnaire

In following we will see if the teachers give a little space to the translation in their classes or not. Since they also give homework maybe they also work on it in their classes too. In the question if they translate texts in class we will see in percentages who translates more in class.

Chart 14. Question 3. Students' Questionnaire

According to this diagram we see that a very high percentage of the secondary and primary school said that they translate also in class which means that the teachers give space to translation in their classes but they just want to have their students more incorporated into translation so this may be a reason why they assign translation also as a homework. Besides these reports, high percentages where teachers work with translation in their classes, the number of those who use Google Translate is still high. In the following we will see if the teachers translate new words for their students or not.

Chart 15. Question 4. Students' Questionnaire

From the answers of the teachers' questionnaires and the discussion made, we understood that they play a role of a dictionary to help their students to understand the words better, so the same statistics can see from this chart where 92% of all the students said that their teachers translates new words for them. Later on we will see if their teachers translate only the word for them or they give the definition of it and the students find out the translation. Besides that we will see what kind of translation the teachers do. The following question is if their teachers translate the whole text for them. This answer might differ in order to make the difference with the previous answer.

The results of this question are not that satisfying since translating the whole text might become the students a bit lazy to understand the philosophy of translation at all. If the teacher serves it in a plate then the students tend to use Google translate in order to complete their task at home since they wouldn't remember the whole text translated in class.

Chart 16. Question 5. Students' questionnaire

From this chart we see that 59% of all the students said that the teacher translates the whole text for them. If this happens in a class then the students do not have the space to ask their teachers for any unknown word or even to try by themselves at the class to translate something. Now let's see how many students ask their teachers for the new words that they have in a text or exercise. And the answers are interesting according to the answers earlier or to be more precise in the question if their teachers translate a whole text for them. The majority of the all the students said that they ask their teachers when they have a new word so 87% of them. This is a bit interesting because a very high percentage of the students said that their teachers translate the whole text and in this question the majority of them say that they ask about new words. This misleads me a bit but it can be that the students ask for the new words but they are not allowed to translate for any kind of reason. So according to the answers so far we can see that the students are interested to learn a new language because they ask their teachers but they also use Google translate if they have any new word.

Chart 17. Question 6. Students' Questionnaire

In the following there is a question to know about the preferences of the students on that how they prefer to have the translation of a word, if they prefer their teacher to give the direct translation of a word, to give the definition of it or they prefer more to use translation applications such as Google translate.

Chart 18. Question 8. Students' Questionnaire

Chart 19. Question 8. Students' Questionnaire

The percentages based on the answers of all students are divided in some same range. So 38% of them would prefer their teacher to give the definition of a word, 36% of them would prefer the teacher to translate the word and 26% of them would prefer to translate the word by themselves in Google translation. Another chart of this question based on the school are as following: 27% of the students from the secondary school would prefer their teacher to translate the word whereas 25% of them would prefer to have the definition of the word and 21% of them would prefer to translate the word by themselves in Google translate. These percentages tell us that there are different students who prefer different things and of course their learning depends on this too. In the other hand 13% of the primary students prefer to have the definition of the new word, 9% of them prefer the teacher to give the translation of the new word and 5% of them prefer to use Google translate. So there is a difference even if the questionnaires are not 50-50, this percentage tells us that the secondary school students tend to use Google translate more than those of primary schools. There can be a lot of reasons why the secondary school students tend to use more the translation application. One of the reasons may be that they feel more as grownups and they tend to ask a friend more than the teacher or in this case Google translate. In the questionnaires were made some questions about use of Google translate on that why they like it more, why they use it and if GT was incorrect anytime.

7. What do you like about using Google translate or translation applications?

- It helps in the sentences that we do not understand
- Its free usage
- Offline usage
- Safe translation
- The speed of translation
- The speed of translation, Its free usage

Chart 20. Question 7. Students' Questionnaire

As we can see the students like it more about its speed of translation and because it is a free app and you can also work offline in it. So also the students know some of the advantages of using GT. This means that the students know this application and that's why they rely on it whenever they need it. We also can see for what do they use it most in their translations.

9. Why do you use Google translate the most?

- To translate chunks of words
- To translate sentences
- To translate the whole text
- To translate vocabulary

Chart 21. Question 9. Students' Questionnaire

So, according to this chart we can see that the students use Google translate mostly to translate vocabulary but other percentages are not very low, where 21% of them use Google translate to translate sentences which is related as translating a whole text. 16% of the students use it to translate a whole text which percentage is not that far from that one of translating the vocabulary. And only 17% of them use Google translate to translate chunks of words.

From all these above answers we saw that students of primary and secondary schools use the Google translate and there is not much to do about it. In the last question for them to see if GT was incorrect anytime we will see their answers about it.

Chart 22. Question 10. Students' Questionnaire

According from this chart we can see that even 69% of all the students said that GT is sometimes inaccurate they still use it. 21% said that GT is often incorrect but they still keep using it. Some of them think that Google translate is never incorrect and only 3 students or 2% of them think that Google translate is always wrong or incorrect. So this diagram makes us think about it. Even if the use of Google translate mislead them, they still continue using it. Why is that so? We have an opinion on that. As teachers said that they do not give lower grades if a student uses it, this makes me think that students keep on using it, because they do not get punished about that. And since the students know that their teachers will help them again in their translation, they see Google translate as an opportunity to learning.

4.7 Comparison of results

Since I had two kinds of questionnaires, one for the teachers and the other for the students, we are making a comparison between these two in order to have a clear result or enough information to the purpose of the study. As mentioned above the purpose of the study is to see the assessment of the translated texts with Google translate by the teachers of primary and secondary schools. For this point we saw that the teachers do not give lower grades if they see a Google translated text from their students. The results are the same from primary and the secondary schools.

Only a small numbers of teachers said that they give lower grades if they see a Google translated text. The comparison of the questionnaires would be also in some other questions based on their answers according to their age, experience, the work of place so if the work in a primary or secondary school and so on. To see a better comparison or in this case to see the similarities in the second question of the questionnaire we will tabulate the results or their opinions.

Question 2. In what cases is it okay to use Google translate?	
Primary school teachers	Secondary school teachers
Anytime you think is necessary.	When pupils want to know the meaning of the words and their usage.
For a particular unknown word, not for a text.	When one wants to get an immediate idea of the translation of a particular word in mother tongue (L1).
I suggest not to use Google translate	Translating words only.
To translate, to pronounce letters, synonyms, antonyms	Short texted translations.

Table 2. Question 2 – Teachers’ questionnaire

In this table we can see more the similarities of the teachers’ opinions based on their place of work. So most of the teachers suggest using Google translate for translating words and not the whole text, others said to use it for orientation, when you have the main idea of the word but you want to be sure of it. Only a small number of teachers suggested not to use Google translate but most of them are pro using it in particular ways.

As we know from the literature review we saw the advantages and disadvantages of using GT. There are also the opinions of the teachers according to the questions about the advantages and disadvantages of Google translate. These results also will be tabulated to see them clearer.

Question 3. For you as a teacher, and fro your pupils, what are the main advantages of using GT	
Question 4. For you as a teacher, and for your pupils, have there been any disadvantages to using online translation applications (e.g. Google translate)	
Advantages of using GT (Teachers’ opinions)	Disadvantages of using GT (Teachers’ opinions)
Basically I think that it is the fastest approachable translator.	It cannot put a translation into proper context without the help of a human
Direct translation, pronunciation of the word, usage of the word.etc	A disadvantage is that pupils most of the time use it to translate sentences and not a word and the again most of the time the translation is not correct.
It is incredibly fast and gives us additional info	If longer paragraphs are processed dir translation, the translation is not reliable.
Finding the translated word, as a different part of speech and used also in examples, sentences.	Another disadvantage is that the pupils do not bother to learn the new word at all or to check if translation is correct because they thinks that since it is a n online program it must be correct.

Google translate is faster than using a dictionary	Being addicted
It gives an opportunity to understand the meaning of the words, it also gives information for that are related to the word	Google translate can sometimes trick you especially if you're a beginner as in many cases translations are inadequate
It offers different meanings of a translated word,	Often no accuracy on translation
It has recently improved in the translation of sentences from English to Albanian and vice versa.	There is a risk of using Google translate, especially when students find comfort in completing their tasks without learning the very same words they have been searching
Practical and available Offline	
You get the exact or close understanding/meaning of a word	It doesn't give you the exact meaning of the whole sentence, just the translation of word by word.
When we don't have enough time	Word order is not correct in most of the cases when you use it for complex or compound sentences

Table 3. Questions 3&4 – Teachers’ Questionnaire

As we see, the teachers’ opinions are close to those of the researchers. They know from their experience since they use Google translate for themselves. Now let’s see the comparison of the answers from the students’ and teachers’ perspective. We’ll see how many teachers and how many students said that they use Google translate.

Chart 23. Question 10 – Teachers’ Questionnaire

Chart 24. Pre-Question – Students’ Questionnaire

As we can see, both the teachers and the students said that they use Google translate. So we can see that GT has a very big impact in our schools. From 80 questionnaires for the teachers there were only one teacher that didn’t answer and 14 of them said that they do not use it, and from the 150 students’ questionnaires, there were only 14 students that said they do not use it. We can see the age of the teachers or their experience in charts to see who use it more, but from this point of view we see that there isn’t something like experience that stops the teachers not to use it. Since the most of them use GT, this means that teachers of different ages are in contact with it as their students as well. As teachers talked about the advantages and disadvantages of Google translate, students also answered to similar questions in their questionnaires. The answers of both the teachers and the students were similar according to the advantages, where students had to answer what they like about GT. As we mentioned the advantages and disadvantages from the teachers’ perspective, now I am going to show a table what the students like about GT and if they saw disadvantages when they used GT.

Question 7. What do you like about using Google translate?
The advantages from the students’ perspective
It helps in the sentences that we do not understand
Its free usage
Offline usage
Safe translation
The speed of translation
The speed of translation, Its free usage
The speed of translation, Its free usage, Offline usage
The translation of foreign languages

Table 4. Question 7 – Students’ questionnaire

As we can see the answers of the students were similar to those of the teachers. As teachers had the question about the disadvantages, the students had to answer in the question if Google translate was inaccurate anytime. They had to answer in a close question where they had to choose, always, sometimes, often or never. And from their answers that were previously showed in a diagram we can see that the majority of the answers were sometimes and often, which means that their answers are again similar to the teachers, because according to their answers Google translate is not accurate in translation as teachers said in their answers that Google translate sometimes fails when it comes to translate sentences or texts.

As we know from our school policy, the students are not allowed to use their phones in class. This means that our students use their phones mostly at home, and when this happens, the students tend more to use GT at home than in class. This is related to homework. If the teachers give assignments in translation, this make our students more addicted to Google translate and of course they would use it more. The researcher wanted to know the teachers' answers according to their experience of teaching, who gives more assignments in translation as homework. To see it better, we have tabulated the results to make the comparison. From 80 questionnaires, 30 of them said that they do not assign and 50 of them said yes.

Question 9. Do you assign words, sentences or paragraphs for students to translate as homework	
Teachers' answers based on their teaching experience	
Teachers' experience	Number of teachers who share the same years of experience
Teachers who assign homework (YES)	
1 years of experience	1 teacher
2 years of experience	3 teachers
3 years of experience	1 teacher
4 years of experience	1 teacher
5 years of experience	5 teachers
6 years of experience	1 teacher
7 years of experience	3 teachers
8 years of experience	1 teacher
9 years of experience	1 teacher
10 years of experience	5 teachers
11 years of experience	2 teachers
12 years of experience	2 teachers
14 years of experience	5 teachers
15 years of experience	1 teacher
18 years of experience	1 teacher
19 years of experience	3 teachers
20 years of experience	4 teachers
21 years of experience	2 teachers
22 years of experience	1 teacher
24 years of experience	1 teacher
25 years of experience	2 teachers
26 years of experience	2 teachers
28 years of experience	1 teacher
29 years of experience	1 teacher

Table 5. Question 9 – Teachers' questionnaire

Question 9. Do you assign words, sentences or paragraphs for students to translate as homework

Teachers' answers based on their teaching experience	
Teachers' experience	Number of teachers who share the same years of experience
Teachers who don't assign homework (NO)	
1 years of experience	2 teachers
2 years of experience	2 teachers
5 years of experience	1 teacher
6 years of experience	1 teacher
7 years of experience	1 teacher
8 years of experience	3 teachers
10 years of experience	4 teachers
11 years of experience	3 teachers
12 years of experience	1 teacher
13 years of experience	1 teacher
15 years of experience	2 teachers
17 years of experience	2 teachers
19 years of experience	1 teachers
20 years of experience	2 teachers
21 years of experience	1 teacher
22 years of experience	1 teacher
30 years of experience	1 teacher
38 years of experience	1 teacher

Table 6. Question 9 – Teachers' Questionnaire

According to the answers of the teachers' experience in teaching we can see that the teachers with more years of experience said that they assign homework to translate. So according to these results we can say that this may be one of the reasons why the students tend to use more Google translate at home in order to complete the assignments given by their teachers. In the earlier question about the grades if teachers give lower grades when they see a Google translated text, the majority of their answers were that they do not give lower grades, they just advise them to not use it or they said that they give advises how to use Google translate in order not to make mistakes during its usage. So according to these results we can say that the students use Google translate because they do not get punished about it in one or another way.

Besides the results of the questionnaire there are also the results of the given texts to the 8th and 10th graders. As we mentioned above the students were not obliged to take part in my study and they also didn't know the purpose of the study. Their teachers gave those texts to their students and when they completed them we went to the schools to make the discussion based on the translated texts by the students. They had 3 days in advance to complete the task and to bring it back to their teachers. There not very many students who took part in this task but to see it better we will tabulate the number of participants, divided in what school were they and from which municipality and grade were they.

The participants are as following:

Number of the students	Type of school	Municipality	Grade
12	Secondary school	Suharekë	10 th
8	Secondary school	Malishevë	10 th
17	Primary school	Suharekë	8 th
14	Primary school	Malishevë	8 th

Table 7. The Number of Participants in the Translated Texts

According to the given translated texts from the students back to their teachers, we discussed with them based on their translations if they used Google translate or not. We will start from the secondary school in Suhareka where the teacher A.B. checked their task and for some texts he said that they used Google translate according to the word order which was not in its place and then some grammatical errors as well. He said that he knows his students and he knows their level of English so it is easier for him to understand who used Google translate and who not. We discussed also about the grading, if he would give lower grades if he sees such of translation from his students, and he said that he normally doesn't assign homework based on translation and so he doesn't give grades about translation. He said that he only asks about translating texts in the end of a period of school and in that way he knows who is progressing in translation. But to answer to my question he said that he would not give lower grade but would advise the students to not use it because he would not assess their tasks if they use Google translate. The other teacher from Malisheva Sh.Th. said that also his students used Google translate and he said that this thing happens 70% of the time. The teacher said that he gives sometimes texts to translate just to see their progress in translating and most of the time students use Google Translate for vocabulary or sometimes even sentences. He said that is a bit hard to avoid it since we live in a time of technology where every student has a mobile phone and since Google translate is a free application; this makes it a way more usable. He said that he also gives such of texts in class to see their level and then compares them to the ones that he assigns as homework. In the question if he gives lower grades when he sees a text translated by Google translate he said that he doesn't because his purpose is just to help his students how to translate and he doesn't give grades at all in translation. The teacher said that he advises them not to rely too much in translation applications and to ask him more or to rely more in dictionaries than online sources.

The other teacher from Suhareka in the primary school S.Sh said the same as her colleagues that the students have used Google translate during the translation and she said that this happens continuously, mostly from the students who have lower grades in English language. The advanced students rely on it only when they have new words but they still use it. She said that nowadays the technology is all around us and the students are those who are more exposed to it. In the question how she reacts when she sees a Google translated text, she said that she advises not to use it but if the students tend to use it often than she said that she tries to advise them how to use it in order to not get misled during its usage. Further more in the question if she uses herself Google

translate she said yes. She told me that she has to use it in order to know better when her students used it and to make a fair assessment toward them.

The last teacher who was interviewed is R.K. from the primary school in Malisheva. He told me that his students used also Google translate to translate the text given by me. He said that it may be because it was something new for them because they only translate texts from their books, and that's why they used Google Translate to complete this task. We asked him if they use Google translate when they have to translate their texts and he said that not much, since they discuss the new words at class and they do not need to rely that much on Google translate, but he admitted that Google translate is among us and the students are aware of it but we as teachers should advise our students not to use it as much as we can because we as teachers can do it. In the question if he gives lower grades to them if he sees a Google translated text or sentence he said no. He tries to advise them not to use it at all because they can ask him for anything they need. So as we saw none of the teachers tend to give lower grades when they assess about translation when they see Google translated texts because they know that using it is something unstoppable since technology is making it hard to avoid. From the abovementioned we saw that almost every single student has a mobile phone and the students tend to use more translation applications or whatever they need. Nowadays everything is easier to learn if the students are interested and even if they use translation applications it has its advantages.

6. Limitations

The main point of our study is the assessment of Google translated texts in primary and secondary schools, where we made research, observation and discussion in 4 schools in two municipalities. The gathering data were in descriptive and comparison method. The teachers were of different ages. Besides the discussion made in the schools we also spread my questionnaires online for the teachers and students as well. From the gathering data we saw that there were 80 questionnaires with teachers of different places from Kosovo, different ages and different experiences in teaching. We wanted to know from my research, if teachers as well the students use Google Translate for different purposes. And yes, the majority of the answers were positive. So no matter their ages, no matter their experience in teaching they still use it and they consider incorporating it also in their teaching but at this point the answers were fifty-fifty. In order to have better result in this question the teachers should have been in equal number depending on the school they work so we would know better if we would have teachers from primary and secondary schools in equal, because there were more than 84% primary school teachers, and this thing has limited a lot of comparison that we could have made on my research. So this is the first limitation that we suggest for further research in the future. There should be equal questionnaires in both primary and secondary schools in order to have better results in some questions. In order to have better results from both teachers and the students on the question if they give lower grades if they see a Google translated text, there should have been a similar question to the students questionnaire just to see the results from the students too.

The majority of the teachers said that they do not react with a lower grade, but they tend to explain to them why they should or shouldn't use Google translate for their assignments. They tell about advantages and its disadvantages of it and they do not assess them with lower grades. But in order to have a better view of this question there should have been the similar question to the students to see if they take lower grades from their teachers. So for further research this question could be added to the questionnaire. Another thing to do in order to have better results could be by spreading the questionnaires for teachers and students in the schools and then we would know better if this phenomenon is happening for real since in my research we have the results only from the teachers' side according to the assessment. In the other hand even if we hadn't that similar question in the students' questionnaire, we can observe that the students don't get lower grades since a very high number of them use Google Translate. This can lead us that if they use Google translate, it means that they do not get punished with grades, and that's why they still keep using it. As we said this is only a conclusion made by me, but if the further research would have the question then the result would be more accurate and real. According to the teachers of the schools where we made our research, from the discussion with them, they agreed that the usage of Google translate is kind of a challenge to fair assessment. Since from their experience they said that Google translate has improved a lot even for our language and this makes it hard to have a fair assessment toward their students. According to them, the formative assessment helps them to know the level of their students and in this way they know when their students might use Google translate for their assignments; otherwise it became a bit hard when translation applications are around us now. For further research in order to know if the teachers make fair assessment if they see a Google translated text should be doing by giving texts to their students to do it at home and then to check if they used GT or not. They could know it by putting the whole text in Google translate to see if they just copy paste it or not and compare their students' homework. To have a fair assessment, two researchers mentioned in chapter 2.3 said that there should be a framework that addresses the pedagogical implications of GT use (certain types of assignments) and they propose to make a list of do's and don'ts in order to assess properly the assignments of the students.

The teachers' questionnaire should have given to me some good results based in experienced and inexperienced teachers, but this did not happen since all of them gave similar answers to one another and some of my questions didn't give the results we expected. For example We wanted to know if the teachers would incorporate the translation applications in their teaching and we expected to have answers like experienced teachers would say yes and inexperienced ones would say no, but what we got in the answers was completely the opposite, where there were teachers from both groups who said yes and no, and we couldn't define properly this answer. The same thing happened to another question. So for further research we suggest to have more given answers to the question made and then maybe we could divide those groups better in order to have better results.

About the lack of prior research studies, we can say that there wasn't that much information. We had to make my research based in the internet mostly, and it was a bit hard to find safe information from there. A lot of pages were limited to give their information. In order to read their research, we had to pay their page and unfortunately we couldn't do it.

The same thing happened to the students' questionnaire, there were 110 students or 73% of them from secondary school and 40 students or 27% of them from primary school. This thing limited the comparison in some questions to take better results. Example in the question if they use Google translate, we wanted to know if students of primary or secondary schools use it more, but we couldn't prove it because the questionnaires weren't equal for both types of schools. So for further research, the questionnaires should be equal in quantity in order to have better results. Another question where we could have made a comparison was if the students ask their teachers when they have new words, but still couldn't give the answer which of the students asked more. In this way we would know if students of secondary or primary schools ask more the teachers and do not use Google translate that much. So for further research, it is very important to have equal questionnaires in quantity in order to have better results in comparison which schools use GT more and the other questions when we had lack of answers to prove my results.

Another limitation is about the other kind of observation to take results from the primary and secondary schools. The texts that were give to translate from the students, had to be checked from their teachers and this was easy because they know the level of their students even if they didn't check them at all. To have better results in this case we should have given the texts of one class to the teacher who doesn't teach them, to see if the teacher would know if the students used Google translate. The ways to check them wouldn't be easy since they would not know the students but would only check the text. They can copy paste the text in Google translate to see how much the students used it. In the other hand the students could have used it only for sentences but this could be checked also, and even if they translated only one word the teacher would know it by checking the word order, grammatical errors, or they could have write one translation of the word but it doesn't fit into that sentence. So the teachers know even if they do not know the level of the student.

So our research has some limitations but we suggested some ways for further research on this topic.

7. Conclusions and recommendations

Google translate is a phenomenon happening in our schools too. Teachers admitted that they cannot do that much in order to avoid it; on the contrary they are trying to help their students to use it properly in order not to get mislead by it. From the discussion made with the teachers, Google translate is a challenge to a fair assessment and this had deeply impacted the teaching and learning environment. Students nowadays use translation application for any kind of purposes in their daily life, but this impacted their learning too.

Since teachers are aware of this phenomenon they started to advise their students how to use it. So they started to give instructions and started to use it for themselves as well, just to see the advantages and disadvantages of it in order to help their students. By using it the teachers can be more aware when students use it for their assignments. Since the most of the teachers assign homework in translating, of course that the number of students that use GT is going to grow day by day and this is not a good thing for us as teachers. We would recommend not to assign translation texts as homework because the beginners tend more to use Google translate and they would rely very much on it, and GT could be very tricky for them. Even if the students use GT, teachers' reactions toward them are not that bad. According to their answers they advise their students not to use it, or they advise them how to use it to have better results and they do not give lower grades about it. My recommendation is that the teachers should have some criteria or frameworks where the students are allowed to do or not to do when they use Google translate. The students should know that if they use GT more than they should, then they would have consequences from their teachers.

The teachers nowadays admit that Google translate is among us and half of them according to the questionnaires see it as a pedagogical tool since not every student has dictionary to learn from. Of course it would be better if students own dictionaries better than smart phones but we're living in technology era and we cannot do that much about it. As students said in their answers, teachers help them in class to translate specific words, sentences or texts. So teachers are those who play the role of a dictionary in their classes. Teachers are doing their best in order to help their students in class to have all the information they need just not to use other translation applications online and they hope that in the future students would be more interested to learn something new in their classes rather than from GT.

The most interesting thing from all the questions was if the GT was ever inaccurate during the translation and majority of the students said that GT was sometimes or often incorrect, but they still use it. We would recommend the teachers to always take their dictionaries in class, to tell the students what are dictionaries, how they should work with one, what it has inside of it and I'm sure that the students would be interested to use one. Let them touch it, learn from it and talk about the importance of dictionaries. It is very normal that nowadays students would use more GT than a dictionary because we as parents offer to them better a Smartphone, an iPad than a book or dictionary. We as parents and as teachers should make our children, students more aware of using books than other sources when they need something to be learned or translated.

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